

Increase cross-border capacity to reduce market splitting of day-ahead electricity markets – A dynamic line rating approach

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Abstract—Market splitting occurs when the energy flow between different market zones is higher than the cross-border capacity, separating the markets and bringing economic losses to market participants. The cross-border capacity is computed by Transmission System Operators using a seasonal steady-state line rating (SLR). SLR considers fixed conservative meteorological conditions throughout the year except for the ambient temperature that can have a fixed seasonal and spatial variation. Dynamic line rating (DLR) analysis using near real-time meteorological data allows to effectively computing the capacity of the lines while SLR, by usually underestimating it, may lead to market splitting. This work presents a case study where DLR is applied to reduce the number of market splitting occurrences in the Iberian market of electricity. For the different scenarios analyzed, the reduction of market splitting occurrences can range from 16% to 57%, being lower than 1% in case of exporting from Portugal to Spain.

Index Terms—Cross-border capacity, Dynamic line rating, Iberian market of electricity, Market splitting, Market zones, Seasonal line rating.

I. INTRODUCTION

Until 2030, the European Union defined ambitious goals concerning the increase in the share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the power system and also about the Internal Market of Electricity to harmonize prices all over Europe, which reinforce the need to increase the national and the cross-border transmission capacity of the grid [1,2].

Traditionally, most Transmission System Operators (TSOs) use a “Steady-State” thermal equilibrium model using reference extreme weather conditions to design the maximum seasonal ampacity allowed *per* overhead power line, known as the seasonal line rating (SLR) [3,4]. They use reference values for the wind speed between 0.5 and 0.61 m/s and the irradiance between 1000 and 1150 W/m². Normally, the reference value of the air temperature is adjusted seasonally and the wind direction is neglected. These values are very conservative and, operationally, the conductor’s ampacity is continuously

changing according to meteorological, physical and electrical factors. The use of numerical dynamic line rating (DLR) models as the IEEE 738-2018 [5], the Kuipers & Brown [6], and the CIGRÉ [7], using near-real-time meteorological data, can overcome the limitation previously identified enabling to optimize the existing asset use [8].

Several studies indicate that on average DLR allows increasing the capacity over the SLR between 10% to 30%, identifying that the line capacity is underestimated around 80% of the time when the increased capacity could avoid congestion and unnecessary curtailments of variable renewable energy (VRE) [8-10]. When the line capacity is overestimated DLR is also important since it safeguards the security of the power system by avoiding the degradation of the lines and line outages [8]. The use of DLR models can be important in the long run by avoiding or postponing, in some cases, the construction of new lines but also in the short run by avoiding market splitting, grid congestion, VRE curtailments, and the degradation of the lines [3,4,8-10].

Traditionally, electricity markets are divided into wholesale and retail markets [11]. In the wholesale market, producers can submit bids to the markets or privately negotiated bilateral contracts with retailers or big consumers. In the retail market retailers and consumers negotiated private bilateral contracts. Then retailers acquire the energy that their consumers require from the electricity markets [12]. The day-ahead market is the most used wholesale market. It is a spot market based on supply and demand bids, and, in Europe, it is cleared using the system marginal pricing theory, which has the goal of increasing the general welfare of market participants [13,14]. TSOs have to evaluate the feasibility of the deals to avoid grid congestion and guarantee the power system security. So, when planning the power flow for such deals they use the fixed “Steady-State” maximum ampacity of the lines thus eventually, making unfeasible some bids, increasing market prices, and reducing the general welfare of the participants [15]. Under such conditions, in coupled

regions, electricity market splitting (MS) occurrences can occur. MS brings economic losses because it affects the merit order of the coupled market by pushing out of the market-clearing some of the most competitive power plants, due to the lack of cross-border capacity to comply with the optimal power flow between market zones, increasing the price difference between them. Furthermore, it also can lead to VRE curtailments because of the lack of cross-border capacity to trade such energy. The cross-border capacity to export and import energy between market zones is not only limited by the physical constraints of the transmission grid but also by commercial reasons.

Against this background, the goal of this work consists in the application of a DLR analysis to assess its potential to reduce the number of hours with market splitting occurrences. The CIGRÉ model [7] implemented in [8] is used to compute the DLR of the interconnecting overhead power lines. The day-ahead market from the Iberian electricity market (MIBEL) is used as a case study. Section 2 presents the methodology used. Section 3 presents the case study and section 4 presents some final remarks.

II. METHODOLOGY

The present methodology uses a DLR analysis to compute the hourly capacity of the transmission lines between different market zones. It follows the steady-state heat balance method recommended by the CIGRÉ model but also includes the internal energy variation (thermal inertia) of the cable when it is not in equilibrium [7]. The thermal behavior of an overhead conductor is calculated as the balance of gained and lost heat due to the weather conditions around the conductor and its electrical load, is described in (1) [5].

$$m \cdot C_p \cdot \frac{dT}{dt} = -P_c - P_r + P_s + P_j \quad (1)$$

Where m is the cable mass (kg/m), C_p is the heat capacity of the cable (J/kgK), T is the temperature (K) and t is the time. P_c is the convective cooling, P_r is the radiative cooling, P_s is the solar heating and P_j is the joule heating (W/m). In this formulation, the radial and axial cable temperature distribution is discarded. In thermal equilibrium (steady-state) the right member of equation (1) takes the value 0. The methodology uses the data from the transmission lines vertex towers split the in-between line section into sectors of 3 kilometres, consistent with the spatial resolution of the meteorological data. When the sector's length is below the 3 km resolution their length is used instead. For each sector, the wind speed and direction, ambient temperature, and solar irradiance are obtained using a numerical weather prediction (NWP) model. The data are extracted for the mid-distance point of each line's sector. Fig. 1 presents the main steps of the methodology. This methodology is implemented to identify the potential benefit of using the DLR. The methodology starts by identifying hours with market splitting.

For these hours, the DLR analysis is implemented to verify if there is an extra capacity for cross-border trade compared with the assumed SLR of each interconnection line. If an extra capacity is effectively available, the day-ahead cross-border capacity between different market zones is recalculated.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the methodology used to analyze the benefits of DLR under periods of market splitting.

Considering the bids of all market zones to a centralized day-ahead market (market coupling) and using a marginal pricing system algorithm [13] it is possible to compute the clearing price, the energy of the coupled market, and the importation (IMP) or exportation (EXP) energy flows between market zones. If these energy flows are higher than the cross-border real capacity between market zones, but not over the legislated power limit, those markets are separated and the clearing price and energy are computed to each market zone, receiving as explicit supply (importing) or demand (exporting) bids of the available energy for cross-border trades. When the DLR is higher than the SLR it is possible to avoid market splitting, in most cases, if the DLR is higher than the required import/export power flow. For cases where is not possible to avoid this interconnection congestion, DLR can contribute to reducing the price difference between market zones by (potentially) increasing the interchange commercial capacity between them.

III. CASE STUDY

This case study focuses on the application of the aforementioned DLR methodology to reduce the occurrence of hours with market splitting in the day-ahead market of MIBEL.

A. Data

This sub-section identifies the meteorological and interconnection lines (tie-lines) data used in the case study.

a) Meteorological data: As needed to establish the daily operating programme by the TSO, a NWP model in real time is used to forecast the meteorological parameters required to compute the DLR. It is used to indirectly compute the DLR without the need for a wide and expensive network of meteorological measure equipment, as discussed in [8]. The NWP is calibrated for the region under analysis using data observed in meteorological masts. It has a spatial resolution of 3 kilometers and provides hourly wind speed and direction, ambient temperature, and solar irradiation data, obtained for a height of 35 m above ground level [15].

b) Tie-lines network data: Both the Spanish and Portuguese TSOs use a projected SLR with pre-set meteorological conditions considering a wind speed of 0.6 m/s and a solar irradiation of 1000 W/m² during the daytime, and zero irradiation during the night. The main difference in the SLR of both countries stands in the definition of ambient temperature. In Portugal, this parameter is defined monthly

while in Spain is defined seasonally. During the summer, these ambient temperatures are also defined spatially according to the climatological average temperatures in each country. The different methodologies used by TSOs originate a slack between their interconnection capacity in May and November, which consists in the capacity difference between serial tie-lines (potentially) originating market splitting. There are lines connecting the Portuguese and Spanish transmission grids. Only nine of them have energy flows. The location, voltage levels, and the names of the twelve substations that connect the nine representative power lines are presented in Fig. 2 [16].

Figure 2. Tie-lines location between Portugal and Spain.

The connections between “Lindoso” and “Cartelle”, and “Pocinho” and “Aldeadávila” have two parallel lines. Table I presents the main characteristics of the interconnection lines. Other transmission system assets like transformers and circuit breakers can also constrain the maximum capacity in each interconnection, as depicted in Fig. 3. In this figure, the total interconnection capacity considering the conductors’ characteristics of each zone and the slack capacity to import or export from Portugal to Spain is presented. This figure highlights the i) different interconnection capacity considered by the two TSOs for the same lines and ii) most of the time the limiting factor is not related with conductors thermal capacity but due to other grid assets with lower ratings as the current transformers limitation on the Portuguese side.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISATION OF THE INTERCONNECTIONS BETWEEN PORTUGAL AND SPAIN.

Tie-line name	Conductor type PT/ES	Maximum Cable Temp. PT/ES [°C]	Ambient Temp. Variation [°C]
Alto Lindoso-Cartelle 1-2	Rail	85	15-29
Lagoaça-Aldeadávila	Rail	85	15-32
Pocinho-Aldeadávila 1-2	Zebra/Lapwing	85	15-32
Pocinho-Saucelle	Zebra	85	15-32
Falagueira-Cedillo	Zambeze	85/70	15-33
Alqueva-Brovales	Rail	85	15-35
Tavira-Puebla de Guzmán	Rail	85	15-32

Figure 3. Total interconnection capacity of each country, and import and export slack from Portugal.

Careful historical analysis of each interconnection power line reveal that during import periods the grid bottleneck is observed in “Alto Lindoso-Cartelle 1-2 (LC)” tie-lines. For periods of energy export from Portugal to Spain, four tie-lines “Pocinho” to “Aldeadávila” and “Pocinho” to “Saucelle” in the so-called “Douro International (DI)” region are the ones that trigger MS. Therefore, the import and export margins are limited by the difference between these tie-lines capacities.

B. Study

The study is conducted for the year 2018, a typical year for hydroelectric and wind power production in Portugal [16]. During this year the number of market splitting hours was 456 (5.2% of the yearly hours). During 283 hours occurred market splitting due to a lack of capacity to import from Portugal to Spain, increasing, on average, 7.16 €/MWh the market price in Portugal. The remaining 173 hours of market splitting are due to export capacity. This situation increased, on average, 3.80 €/MWh the market price in Spain [17]. Fig. 4 presents the 2018 hourly import and export capacity of Portugal [16].

Figure 4. Hourly import and export programmed capacity of Portugal in 2018.

Analyzing Figs. 3 and 4 can be verified that only around one-third of the tie-lines capacity is available for trading in 2018 due to commercial and security reasons. Part of this capacity is reserved for bilateral contracts and ancillary services exchanges which limit the cross-border capacity available in the day-ahead market increasing the likelihood of MS. To identify the potential benefit of DLR analysis to reduce

the number of hours with market splitting in the day-ahead market, the following three scenarios were analyzed:

- Baseline: current values used by both TSOs based on an SLR analysis;
- A: Portugal uses its capacity slack limited to the DLR outputs;
- B: Both countries use the DLR and upgrade other transmission system assets (as transformers and circuit breakers) that have lower ratings. In this scenario, the cable's maximum ampacity is the only constrain.

C. Results

Applying the DLR methodology to the congested interconnection power lines is possible to verify that their capacity is higher than the projected SLR capacity during 384 (84%) hours of the 452 market splitting hours. Considering the 72 hours that DLR is lower than SLR, 60 of them occurred in the LC tie-lines and the other 12 in the DI region.

Fig. 5 presents the extra capacity that can be obtained by applying the DLR considering the slack between tie-lines (scenario A) and without limitations (scenario B).

Figure 5. Extra capacity from congested tie-lines using DLR in 2018.

Analyzing Fig. 5 can be concluded that other required assets of tie-lines as the current transformers strongly limit the tie-lines capacity. Considering scenario A, during 384 hours the DLR of the tie-lines is higher than the SLR. In 50% of this time, an increase of the tie-lines capacity in 164 MW was attained. As expected, by applying the DLR without limitations (scenario B), the median tie-lines capacity increases to 796 MW. Using the system marginal pricing algorithm to compute the clearing price and energy of the coupled day-ahead market of MIBEL it is possible to verify a median lack of cross-border capacity around 480 MW. Scenarios A and B show a reduction in the occurrence of hours with MS by 16% and 57%, respectively, assuming no additional limitations from the remaining Portuguese and Spanish power lines. The median value of the tie-lines capacity in scenario B is higher than the medium capacity needed to avoid market splitting. However, they are not correlated, which means that in some hours the DLR gain is higher than needed and in the other hours it is lower than needed. Fig. 6 presents the extra capacity and the capacity in need to avoid market splitting in both scenarios.

Figure 6: Extra capacity (positive) and capacity needed (negative) to avoid market splitting in 2018 after the application of the DLR

Analyzing Fig. 6 it is possible to verify that only in a few occurrences the extra capacity obtained in scenario A can achieve the values of scenario B and the same is true concerning the capacity in need, where scenario B is favorable.

To completely avoid market splitting in cases of importation from Portugal there is a need to increase the capacity on the region “Alto Lindoso-Cartelle (LC)” by 2239 MW and 1889 MW in case of scenarios A and B, respectively. In the “Douro International (DI)” region the capacity should be increased by 2186 MW to avoid market splitting in cases of exportation from Portugal. TSOs should perform a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) to study the best investment scenario against the economic losses that market splitting brings. Fig. 7 presents the monotone curves of the capacity required to avoid MS in the tie-lines that lead to it.

Figure 7: Monotone curves of the capacity needed for each congested zone, DI and LC, on scenarios A and B to avoid MS occurrences.

Assuming a reasonable value of occurrence of only 1% (87 yearly occurrences) of market splitting, in the case of exportation from Portugal to Spain, it is possible to avoid market splitting by using the DLR in the “Douro International (DI)” region - see blue solid line B(DI). Otherwise, it will be necessary to invest in 253 MW of new transmission capacity to suppress MS occurrences - see orange solid line A(DI). Furthermore, in the case of the highest capacity in need, the use of DLR did not provide any extra capacity and the results suggest that when Portugal imports from Spain, is not possible to suppress the market splitting using only DLR. However, it

is possible to reduce the need for new capacity in the north tie-lines from 1066 MW to 867 MW (see dotted lines A(LC) and B(LC), respectively) through the uprating of existing power grid assets.

In conclusion, the use of the DLR approach presented in this work can allow avoiding the construction of new tie-lines with 452 MW, considering the existence of market splitting during 1% of the time during one year. If a value of 2% of MS is assumed, no additional capacity is needed during the exportation periods. For the import cases, the additional capacity identified is 306 MW only if not uprating grid assets, otherwise, it is possible to completely avoid the construction of new lines by using DLR.

IV. FINAL REMARKS

The use of a conservative seasonal line rating (SLR) approach to compute the day-ahead lines' capacity by Transmission Systems Operators (TSOs) can limit the interconnection capacity during some hours leading to market splitting occurrences. This paper analyzed the impact of a dynamic line rating (DLR) analysis to mitigate market splitting between coupled regions. Market splitting originates economic losses due to a lack of cross-border capacity between market zones.

This paper defines a case study where a DLR analysis is used to mitigate the number of market splitting occurrences in the day-ahead market of the Iberian electricity market (MIBEL) during 2018. Two scenarios were defined and compared with the SLR approach. In 2018, 456 hours of market splitting occurred on the MIBEL's day-ahead market. For these hours, the DLR analysis shows during 384 hours (84% of time) an interconnection capacity above the values obtained with the SLR. Due to the limitations of other transmission grid assets (as transformers and circuit breakers), the use of a DLR analysis can only mitigate 16% of the market splitting occurrences (scenario A), otherwise, it can be reduced by 57% (scenario B). The results suggest that upgrading the grid assets and using DLR (scenario B) would contribute to an occurrence of market splitting when exporting from Portugal to Spain lower than 1% of the time during one year. For importing cases, to obtain a frequency of occurrence below 1%, a cross-board capacity of 867 MW in the north tie-lines was needed.

Results suggest that the use of a DLR analysis strongly increased the efficiency in the use of the lines' capacity. This approach enables avoiding, in some hours, the cross-board congestion and the associated costs associated with the common SLR analysis. Nevertheless, upgrade other grid assets with lower ratings to avoid a limitation of the DLR lines' capacity can prevent the occurrence during some hours. Even with this update, market splitting will occur. Thus, a CBA analysis is needed to identify the benefit from investment in new interconnection power lines.

Although a long period is needed to obtain results with statistical significance, the results suggest that a real-time DLR approach can contribute to help in alleviating bottlenecks in interconnections and other limiting branches in electricity markets that are currently responsible for limiting their full competitiveness.

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